

Biometrics and AI in Health Care Industry

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Abstract

In the present scenario, health has become a major aspect for each and every individual. From clinics to hospitals healthcare has become an important part. The number of patients waiting for a doctor is constantly increasing for even their regular medical check-up, which can be unnecessary wastage of time just to consult a doctor for simple health issues. To avoid this, automated machines can be used to diagnose a patient's health and generate a report. But doing them at a faster rate and with high accuracy is the challenging task. Usage of machine learning here in clinical informatics and healthcare systems is becoming the near future. Biometric data can be used to retrieve a patient's previous health records with the help of biometric security systems (which cannot be replicated or the data cannot be stolen by anyone). The biometric system can also be used with temperature detection, stress level measurement and for checking the pulse rate of our body. It can also predict a person's health based on the shape of their face by using the technology of deep learning and facial recognition algorithms. In this paper, we discuss the use of biometrics and artificial intelligence in the field of healthcare that can diagnose a patient's health, without them having to wait for a doctor.

Keywords: Clinical informatics, Healthcare Systems, Biometric Systems, Facial Recognition, Deep learning, and Artificial intelligence.

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Introduction

Medical informatics deals with the study and research of application of Information technology in the field of medical science. Here we explain how biometrics can be used in medical science to detect a person's health and improve the way of how general treatments can be done in a better and faster way, providing greater results. Hospitals have become like a second home to people nowadays, the number of patients is increasing rapidly. This has resulted in the huge storage and manipulation of data. Hence it has become the most targeted sector to breach and steal data in today's world. So the use of Biometric has come into picture which uses fingerprints of the patient to access the data which makes it safe and secure (The data integrity is maintained) and it is comfortable for the patient as all their previous health-care records are available at fingertips. The development and usage of Biometrics are constantly increasing; it has extended its roots to recognizing body temperature, stress level measurement and pulse rate of the body. The data collected is configured through deep learning and Artificial intelligence mechanisms.

Role of Deep learning

Deep learning is a form of machine learning. It is used to solve problems which cannot be done by machine learning. It uses neural networks to provide accurate results and increase the computational work. It is used in healthcare by analyzing patient's disease through multiple visions in order to identify the various types of symptoms that a patient is suffering from and then relates them together to identify the type of disease he is suffering from accurately. This in turn helps the doctor to treat the patient better, thus resulting in improved medical decisions. Artificial Intelligence is used to sense and record what different diseases look like and accurately identify them even better the next time.

For example: In an image recognition system, the raw input is given in a matrix of pixels and then the first layer may abstract the pixels and encode its edges; the second layer composes it and encodes the arrangements of edges; the third layer may encode the nose and eyes; and then finally the fourth layer may recognize that the image contains a face. In the case of a disease, the dots are the symptoms and related disorders. If the symptoms are cough, sneezing, sore throat: Then the disorder is identified as a cold.

Survey

Some of the recent investigations in the healthcare industry are as follows:

- Ford is working on a system that integrates various biometric measurements like pulse, galvanic skin response, and breathing rate to determine the driver's "workload," a concept that relates to attention and performance behind the wheel in a curious manner.

Figure 1 Ford Biometric Seat Research

- Researchers used the facial recognition software to successfully diagnose a rare, genetic disease in Africans, Asians and Latin Americans by the National Institute of Health along with their collaborators
- In 2012, Huang, Bartlett and a team of researchers launched a five-year National Institutes of the Health-funded project to determine a patient's pain. The prototype software was programmed to recognize 20 facial muscle movements known to indicate pain.
- Dr. Ian Stephen of Macquarie University in Sydney, Australia along with his colleagues has developed a computer model that can determine the information about a person's health by just analyzing their face. In the facial shape analysis survey conducted by him and his colleague found out that it could accurately detect a person's health by analyzing their face.

Applications of Biometrics in Health care

- The stress level management is measured by the change in the interval between heartbeats, known as heart rate variability which is measured by using the thumb. The "stress sensors" are still in their earliest stages of development.
- A robust peg free camera set up is employed for infrared thermal imaging. A 3D dataset of the image is extracted from the vein patterns. Multiple features are extracted from the real parts of the convolved images using the proposed branch point based feature extraction techniques.
- The metal plates that are built can sense pulse and skin conductivity. In addition, infrared can sense changes in body and skin temperature relative to the room temperature.
- The thermal infrared is used in face detection problems. Due to its physiology, a typical human face consists of hot and cold parts. Hot parts correspond to tissue areas that are rich in the vasculature (e.g., periorbital and forehead). Cold parts correspond to tissue areas that feature either sparse vasculature or multi-sided exposure to the environment (e.g., cheeks and nose). This casts the human face as a bimodal distribution entity.

Figure 2 The various Biometrics used in Healthcare

Strength

- The patient’s safety is put into a higher level through the use of biometric systems for secure identification.
- Using expert system, the right data can be obtained without any mistakes or manipulation.
- The patient can have access to health care services in much more comfortable way i.e. they need not carry any physical documents with them.
- The time of analyzing and processing data is reduced which indeed results in an improved care which is more efficient and error-free information.
- Patients use the biometric system as a way to protect themselves against fraud and safeguard their identity.
- Patients can receive more successful treatments, as there are no medical errors and inconsistencies in the medical history. This can indeed improve their quality of life.

Challenges

- Storing the entire fingerprint or facial image is not only insecure but also requires huge storage capacity for large user population.
- Biometric devices and sensors are expensive to install at hospitals.
- The usage of patients with these machines might be more distasteful if they are not handled with care and maintained regularly.
- A human touch is required to increase the outcome of a treatment, which is disgruntled when using machines.

The Future in Healthcare

- Artificial Intelligence can assist healthcare practitioners in using medical knowledge to improve the patient outcomes. These systems are loaded with thoroughly analyzed and memorized medical knowledge, and thus providing an excellent clinical and medical solution
- The key reason for the wide adoption and successive growth of AI in healthcare industry will be because it can produce excellent patient outcomes with reduced treatment costs and elimination of unwanted hospital procedures, which indeed improves the hospital workflow and treatment plans is turned towards patient-centric.
- IBM Watson for Oncology is developing an advanced ability to combine the attribute from a patients file with clinical expertise, external research and data which then identifies the potential treatment plan that is essential for the patient.
- The ‘cognitive health assistant’ Medical Sieve is a project which is being built by IBM to assist in clinical decision making in radiology and cardiology. It is built to analyse radiology image to spot and detect problems faster and more reliably. Where, Radiologists would have to only look at the most complicated cases where human supervision is required.
- By the year 2030, Cognitive systems can be used to diagnose chronic conditions such as cancer and diabetes within minutes by providing real-time 3D images and identifying their physiological characteristics in the scans.

Figure 3 Cognitive Prosthesis

Conclusion

The usage of Biometrics and Artificial Intelligence in healthcare will lead to great evolution in the field of medical science, which will indeed make the Doctors to be more competitive. The biometric devices are used to identify and input the readings, which is then processed by Artificial Intelligence accurately and then deep learning. The diagnostics are made faster, cheaper and accurate than ever before. The only difference between a physician and deep learning algorithm is the physician needs to sleep and the algorithm once given runs (and improves) on continuously.

Note: The reports generated by these machines are only generic. The people are advised to not

be dependent on machines for major medical emergencies as they are only at their early stages of development are not programmed to handle emergency situations.

Figure 4 Biometric Market Analysis

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